

ANALYSIS OF STYLISTIC MEANS AND FEATURES OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG'S POEMS

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Abstract: The main feature of the poetry of the 60s-70s of the last century lies in the increasingly diverse and in-depth connections with the surrounding reality. It allows you to feel the fullness of life, the joy of overcoming and victories, the bitterness of losses and defeats, instills in a person a sense of ownership of time, forms an active life position. Alexander Feinberg considered the topic of war sacred for himself, i.e. sacred, and illuminated it in poetry and cinema in its own sublime and truthful way, sometimes in a childish way directly or philosophically generalized, with broad strokes, as in a poem.

Key words: artistic system of A. Feinberg, fresh rhyme, free sonnets, implicit parallelism, artificial stylization, satirical poems.

INTRODUCTION

Alexander Arkadevich Feinberg himself during his lifetime was in every possible way against the scientific approach to his work. He did not like anyone to sing praises to him or, even worse, prematurely write him down in the "bronze" classics of Soviet poetry. The poet was more concerned about the fate of his books and each new poem,

not yet written, hatched inside a successful line or a fresh rhyme found, an innovative unusual poetic form of “free sonnets” [1].

In the table of contents of Alexander Feinberg's poetry collections, instead of the usual headings, there are sometimes numbers - 1941, 1942, 1943, 1952. They are partly recognizable. These are the dates of world history and these are the childhood years of the poet. Time was beating here, and the poet was looking for the main thing for himself in it. Hence the combination in the lyrical hero of a child, a teenager from the past and an adult peering into the past [2]. The author's credo is known - inviolability to "alien thoughts, someone else's anvil, someone else's stubble" and staying within one's own limits - "any field, but mine."

METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

In the children's world of A. Feinberg, the details are calmly descriptive. Implicit parallelism reinforces fundamental incompatibility: «Начальник стругает прутик. Горит золотая фикса... Наша училка по русскому – это соседа жена. Заплаканная и грустная стоит у ворот одна». It is in these "maturing" verses that an interest in sound and the word arises. Usually what mom and dad say. But here the turtledove calls the turtledove - it is necessary to pay attention to bird signals, which are quite common. The cry at the first moment is always alarming. The song motive can spin in the head even regardless of our desire. But Klavdiya Shulzhenko reminds - "we don't need to read our old letters." And Leonid Utyosov will not forget: “There is a sea in which I swam and drowned, and, fortunately, I was pulled ashore. There is air that I breathed in as a child and could not breathe enough...” All this, of course, is in the subtext, but there is a context to expand perception [2].

“The poet is within the culture of the East, and yet, at the same time and in parallel, is a representative and bearer of Russian culture” [3]. This, in my opinion, is the main key to understanding why, in the comprehensive concept of the Motherland, it is the East that the poet assigns the main role and thereby creates a qualitatively new voluminous artistic space. The East, as a living clear crossroads of many cultures

without excessive exoticism and artificial stylization, is revealed to us in verses: "I love morning markets" ("Cycling Tracks"), "Old Song", "Samarkand Bazaar", "Picture of Samarkand Bazaar", "Two Georgians"; in the realities of his native city of Tashkent: "1943", "Forget-Me-Not". "From the station I..." "Tram Park" "A view from childhood", "The city that you are", "5th passage of Zhukovsky", "City dear".

The model of the highest creation of nature is revealed in the poetic landscapes "Pamir", "Above the black-eyed country", "Devil's log", "Chimgan", "Night in the mountains", etc.

G. Malykhin singles out the motives "Man (more precisely, the artist) and power", "Poet and time" in the late works of A. Fainberg of the eastern cycle, written in the 70-80s. XX century: these are "Minaret", "Basilica", "Conqueror", "Invasion of May 11, 1842" about the feat of the ruler of the medieval city, the poet Nadira. These works confirm the immutability of the life and creative position of the poet, his moral principles, implicated in justice, which determine everything and everything in his life and work - from the first to the last line, even in drafts, to which he attached great importance: die before you burn the drafts."

The poem "The String of the Rubaiyat" was associated with the defining actual theme "East-West" in the work of A. Feinberg and its completely new ontological interpretation. It was written in 1978 and published more than 15 years later in 1992 in the prestigious Moscow short-circulation magazine Megapolis. The second and third editions took place in the poetry collection "Priisk" (2000), and later in the collections "List" (2008) and the posthumous two-volume "Poems. Poems. Free Sonnets (2009), which A. Feinberg at the end of his life, being already seriously ill, managed to personally prepare for publication. [3]

National poet of Uzbekistan A. Aripov thanks A. Feinberg for his respect for the Uzbek people and their culture, for his loyalty to the invincible cheerful spirit of Afandi in his satirical poem "The String of the Rubayat", and in another cited article "My countryman" calls him "not a slogan internationalist", but a "real countryman" [4].

DISCUSSION:

The evolution of the artistic system of A. Feinberg reflects the stages of the concept of the world, shows the connection between the history of the lyrical hero and the fate of the poet, determines the forms of figurative and thematic synthesis of the Russian and Eastern cultural worlds. In the space of the poet's lyrical rethinking, - the author claims, - there were Russia and the East, oceans and mountain peaks, skies and deserts, cozy city courtyards, steppe roads scorched by the sun [5]. Freely navigating in this world, respecting the primordial way of life of any people in its moral foundations, the poet gained a sense of universal understanding and the path to world renewal.

CONCLUSION:

In Feinberg's poetry, the past and the present, the West and the East, nationality and internationality intertwine, creating a unique artistic world. Feinberg's lyrical hero is a generous person who has fully preserved his human essence in the age of historical and social chains, is ready to extend a hand of compassion and help to others, and at the same time suffers from the unpleasant events and incidents that are happening in the world. Feinberg's poetry combines the best artistic experiences of Russian and European poets. The traditions of Eastern classical poetry are not alien to his creative style. The poet's work is prolific and extensive. Color, philosophy, depth, clarity of feelings shine in his poems. The poet feels the word deeply, and the reader accompanies this feeling. He lived and created in Uzbekistan. The air, the sky, the soil, the people, in a word, the whole being of this country is as dear to the poet as poetry, as dear as the heart. This can be seen in the warmth of the poet's lines and works, their height hits our breath.

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